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IDENTIFYING GOOD PRACTICES WHEN IMPLEMENTING STORYTELLING IN THE EFL CLASS

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Introduction

We all share stories. We construct internal tales to help us make sense of the world. In a way, we are all storytellers of different sorts. By telling stories we are doing a lot more than making use of a powerful communication vehicle; stories allow us to share information, experiences and feelings in engaging ways (Denning, 2001, p. XV) by creating emotional connections. Thus, storytelling should not just be regarded as an exceptional ingredient of the human experience, it is a part of being human.

In addition, recognizing the potential of storytelling in the education of young children (Phillips, 2000) is also a must not solely because we can regard it as the foundation of virtually all academic disciplines but because it contributes to nurturing primary age kids in many senses -it allows children to learn about the world around them and about life in general, to share and discuss ideas and feelings, to ask and answer each other's questions, all of which promote a prosocial attitude and fosters collaborative learning. Interestingly, tales told by teachers in class can ignite individual self-expression and creativity. Schiro (2004) has acknowledged the invaluable educational importance of oral stories within the classroom due to its power to contextualise information, thus allowing both teacher's and learners' (intellectual, emotional, and physical) engagement with the learning objectives. Carey (1989) brings to light how stories can create social practices and human relations that help constitute reality (p. 86). Stories offer young learners an approachable and exciting way to read, write and learn about an endless quantity of topics.

Of remarkable interest for us language teachers is the impact that storytelling has particularly on reading and writing literacy, as it is paramount and has a substantial effect not exclusively on language acquisition but on the development of children and young people. In fact, Bransford, Brown, & Cocking (1999: 105-108) talk of storytelling as a "bridge" between the physical world and an imaginative one and highlight its potential to introduce children to the initial stages of communication and literacy.

In short, storytelling plays a pivotal role in everybody's life from childhood through adulthood. Dramatizing stories, on another note, has got beneficial impact on the social and cognitive development of children (Wright et al., 2008).

Considering foreign language (from this point onwards, FL) learning in particular, we should never overlook the extent to which understanding oral messages is critical for the success of the rest of the skills of any language. The process of developing successful listening ability also implies the effective acquisition aspects such as identifying the correct pronunciation of words, stress, intonation, language in use, communicative functions, idioms, or vocabulary, just to mention but a few. Consequently, pushing the listening skill of students should be a central part of every language teacher

agenda; subsequently, every technique that contributes to boost listening comprehension should be considered as a building block in L2 classes (Dunkel, 1991).

Offering a variety of listening opportunities to our learners will lead to the enhancement of this important skill. In effect, research has proved that when teachers provide students with a myriad of occasions to accumulate practice in listening, the process of developing useful listening strategies is best achieved. Additional to the idea of the accumulated experience as a must for developing listening, is the belief on the need to maximising the learning experience in itself to optimise learning (Dewey, 1933, Kolb, 1984). Taking advantage of the undeniable interest and/or enjoyment in stories, teachers who include storytelling in their classroom activities are contributing to enhance their students' listening skills (for example, Delano, 1977; Mottley & Telfer, 1997; Bendt and Bowe, 2000; Terblanche, 2002; Douglas, 2005; Simmons, 2006; among many others).

All things considered, the prevalence of storytelling as an invaluable teaching resource goes beyond shadow of a doubt. The question then is to what an extent the actual way in which teachers approach and implement storytelling may bring about different results in the outputs attained.

The research question

As stated above, lots of teachers incorporate storytelling in their teaching. They rely on this technique as a powerful resource for bringing about the most positive outcomes in their students' learning. Nevertheless, the realisation that many other factors (whether the learners' interest is really encouraged, whether the connections created between students and language is really strong, relevant and/or meaningful enough, or, say, whether the tales are told under the best circumstances, among multiple others) could influence on the eventual success of the learning experience and that not every story told in the EFL class always promotes the intended learning, has arisen awareness on the need for teachers to perform in a given way when implementing storytelling. No need to say, teachers should be specifically trained for being successful storytellers, which means to be good performers that select appropriate stories (Dujmovic, 2006). In any case, the identification of good teaching practices with storytelling is of uppermost relevance.

The goal of the current article is to identify those Storytelling approaches, procedures and/or practices that lead to the best results in the EFL Primary class and to draw some implications for the FL class.

The research method

With all the above points in mind, we decided to talk to expert teachers who stand out for their good teaching results and for their students' satisfaction with their classes. All of them (we interviewed four teachers) shared their confidence in the potential of storytelling as a very effective teaching technique for young learners to learn a foreign language.

We made use of a semi-structured interviewed in which our informants were asked to talk basically on 5 main aspects (namely, (i) what storytelling is and what it is not; (ii) the importance of this technique in their classes and the frequency of implementation; (iii) the potential benefits of storytelling in the FL class; (iv) whether any kind of precautions should be taken when selecting and putting this technique into practice; and (v) the ideal way to implement storytelling in the FL class), while always giving them freedom to extend, elaborate, deepen or add anything they may find of relevance.

Results and discussion

Defining the scope of the term storytelling is the first question of interest that immediately stood out. It is often the case that people use the words "storytelling" and "reading aloud" interchangeably. Whereas the features of reading a story aloud may seem similar to those of storytelling however the first one can by no means be considered exactly like a well-told story. They are two separate entities with differences between both. Thus, while the teller of a story is not constrained by what has been written, the one who reads the story is bound -in other words, the reader needs to have the book to read from the printed page. The storyteller is not only not limited by written sentences but he may also include variations in the way he performs, and decide whether to stand or to sit, whether to use the body, eyes, and voice as aids in expression, whether to watch his audience, whether to pay attention to their reactions to the story, etc. The story teller can add as many personal

touches to the story as he wants and make the story his own. This can facilitate the adaptation of the story, to make it suitable to the audience and their language ability -in this sense, the need to ensure adapted activities which can encourage everyone's full development was agreed by all the informants. Pursuing effective and inclusive teaching by adapting practices to fit our learners' on-going learning is not a new idea but had been already pointed out in the literature on successful teaching (Arthur, Grainger & Wray, 2006). Given what has been said, storytelling could work as a suitable way to involve every student in class and to work towards diversity within their school curriculum (Canals et al., 2021).

The notion of meaning also came up early on in the interview. In this regard, teacher C stated: "storytelling is not just telling a story for the sake of it or to fill in lesson time. The stories must be presented in such a way that they are capable of creating a personal meaning for the listener" whereas teacher A remarked on the availability of stories which are not valid because they would not make sense to their students and added: "I consider it essential to know how to choose adequate, meaningful and relevant stories for the learners I teach".

As regards the benefits children experience as a result of storytelling, all our interviewees have agreed that there are multiple outcomes at different levels. Teacher B said: "If you ask me about the effect that storytelling has on my students' learning, I would never end to talk about them all; there are so many benefits that love this technique". Literature in the field had already documented rich results from cognitive, to social, creativity, literacy, or enhancement of home-school relationships, among others (for example, Engel, 2005; Curenton, 2006; Lash, 2008; Genishi & Dyson, 2009;).

On the other hand, class time seems to be a factor that conflicts with the frequency of storytelling use in the FL class. Definitely, storytelling is a time-consuming technique. Teachers blame lack of time for the fact that the tales cannot be present more often in their classes. This reinforces the importance of identifying good practices of this technique. Because of the time it takes to implement it properly, it is important to know how to put it into practice correctly in order not to waste class time.

In relation with time, too, teachers claimed that "it's absolutely vital to spend enough time choosing the most appropriate story" (as declared by teacher E). In this regard, teacher C said: "I am very careful and take a lot of time when I want to choose a story for my class, since I feel most of the stories that can be found in the market are written in such a way that they are too hard to be fully understood by FL students". All in all, when choosing storytelling, teachers must be aware of the investment of in-class and out-of-class time they will have to make as it entails the dedication of extensive time. Only if the selection is made carefully will students be provided with the tools for developing receptive language and they will be able to repeat linguistic forms, incorporating all that they are learning to their linguistic and communicative competence (Dujmovic, 2006). If the aim of the practice is a really comprehensive and meaningful language learning, we must offer our students adequate and attractive contents which are appropriate for their personal and educational stage, needs and interests.

Of great relevance were also our informants' continuous comments on how storytelling brings together many of the circumstances that favour children's learning. In fact, as Moon (2000, p. 3) points out, young learners learn a foreign language through being motivated, by listening and repeating, by imitating the teacher, by doing and interacting with each other in an atmosphere of trust and acceptance, through a variety of interesting and fun activities for which they see the purpose (among others) and according to the teachers we interviewed, when implementing storytelling in the FL class, all these factors are fostered.

We do not want to conclude without highlighting one more advantage that should be attributed to the correct implementation of storytelling: all the teachers we interviewed agreed that effective storytelling allows the creation of a psychologically secure and encouraging setting in the classroom that enhances learning.

Let us not neglect the fact that learning occurs through communication between people, telling and listening to stories, since it is an interactive process in which learners must have a chance to experiment with language in rewarding contexts. Teachers' role involves abilities for presenting,

explaining and illustrating concepts in a way which allows students to be meaningfully engaged in the learning process (Arthur, Grainger and Wray, 2006). This is not possible if teachers don't promote environments in which learners can adopt positive attitudes towards learning, giving them opportunities to feel safe and in which there are prospects for growing up with good feelings.

If students feel at home in class, they are likely to participate, take risks and learn as a result of their involvement in what is taking place in class. However, when students suffer feelings of anxiety, shame and/or inferiority, these often lead to low self-confidence which, in its turn, may lead learners to feel poorly equipped to actively engage in class activities which use English as the vehicle of communication. Due to the fact that language learning is often stressing, students who feel demotivated, frightened, embarrassed or insecure often show overt reluctance to take part in class activities, and thus their progress in language gets inhibited.

Learners' emotional states and responses should never go unnoticed or be underestimated by teachers in the FL class (Kramsch, 1993) especially when it comes to negative feelings that may slow down or stop their learning process (Krashen, 1985). Krashen's (op.cit.) Monitor Model, in spite of having been severely criticised on several grounds by L2 researchers and theorists alike, claiming that it is marked by serious flaws (according to Gregg (1984) Krashen's theory makes use of undefined or ill-defined terms and unmotivated constructs, shows lack of empirical content and thus of falsifiability, and lack of explanatory power, too (p.94), is also a well-known source of ideas for translating theory about 2LA into best classroom practices. In Krashen's philosophy, we can find the "so-called" affective filter hypothesis, according to which a kind of "mental block" can control the access of comprehensible input to the Language Acquisition Device (LAD) for acquisition. This idea explains, according to Krashen, how motivation and other students' factors (for instance, attitude, interest, anxiety, or self-confidence) impact on a learner's ability to learn a FL. Storytelling, when best implemented, allows teachers to enhance their students' learning experience through pleasurable and meaningful class practice while addressing attitudinal factors that affect a learner's learning of a FL allows at the same time. Interestingly, Xiaoqiong and Xianxing (2008) argue that a learner's motivation is vital in learning English, and therefore teachers should acknowledge low motivation as one of the key issues that can impede the learning of a language.

Then, as explained along these lines, teachers need to be sensitive to all pupils' feelings, and they should be ready to find appropriate support systems to alleviate their students' distress whereas providing materials that may foster their interest and motivation; in this regard, storytelling is an invaluable tool to develop different sequences of learning experiences in which students may feel happy and secure, with many chances to get fully engaged and on-task, thus enjoying and benefitting from learning. Through the simplification, interaction and affordability of comprehensive language, storytelling techniques offer FL teachers multiple possibilities to create those contexts in which their students may learn the most by feeling in the right mood and without pressure.

Storytelling supports students' language learning by encouraging them to make sense of what they listen to, to organize and express their ideas and knowledge in a distinctive and meaningful way, and to interact with their classmates around the topic of the story being told. It has also proven to be a powerful resource for inspiring teachers to engage in genuine conversation with their young audiences and to teach them and facilitate the comprehension of the story's facts and messages (Kosara & Mackinlay, 2013).

Concerning language learning in particular, we should highlight that this technique implies a deeper and more correct knowledge of the FL, mainly in terms of orality. Prosody elements play a fundamental role in how the message is transmitted and how students received it, increasing both attention and understanding levels. Intonation, stress, rhythm, tone and length determine the success of the practice, since the exposition to the oral foreign language supports the acquisition of all those phonetic and prosodic features of the target language, which are relevant for a successful communicative process (Kuronen and Tergujeff, 2020).

We have already referred before to why stories being told in class mean an exceptional instrument for acquiring language in a natural and dynamic way, given that they allow the presentation and reinforcement of essential linguistic patterns, key vocabulary and functional

language, causing an ongoing use of language both receptively and productively (Dujmovic, 2006). Actually, its relevance and potential in this regard lies in the possibility that storytelling offers of establishing connections between children's implicit language and the new one, broadening and modifying previous knowledge structures. Moreover, building learning through social interaction allows students to understand or see from the new perspective of others, engaging in deep learning processes and discovering and incorporating others' views (Liu and Lan, 2016). In fact, one of the needs addressed by constructivist perspectives in learning regards teaching students how to "work together to solve problems through group-based, cooperative learning activities" (Roblyer & Edwards, 1997, p. 51). Collaborative and group-based activities, such as the ones teachers can decide after students have listened to a story being told, can promote prosocial behaviour, or "positive social interaction skills such as cooperation, sharing, kindness, helping, showing affection, and verbalizing feelings (Calvert, 1999, p. 209), so the effect of storytelling goes further beyond language acquisition in itself. Moreover, to select concrete students grouping and to foster a classroom's climate that invites concentration and calm will weigh in the good development of the dynamics.

Conclusion

Child's education is an essential foundation for future child development. With everything we have been noting along this paper we have claimed that the careful, precise implementation of storytelling can provide teachers with a reliable technique conducive to quality learning among learners. Storytelling brings lots of benefits for obtaining a good social and emotional development, encouraging positive relationships between learners and teachers and it must help us as an educational resource that inspires children to create and imagine, empowering learners and critiquing prevailing ideas and social practices (Beck & Kosnik, 2006).

All in all, every teacher should be acknowledged with the essentials of good practices to implement storytelling because (i) it brings about very good results in the students' language learning, (ii) it encourages interest and motivation for class activities, (iii) it makes students feel relaxed and calm, ready to learn, (iv) it strengthens cognitive and social connections on the part of learners and (v) it empowers children in general.

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